

EXPERIENCES OF SECURITY GUARDS SERVING IN DIOCESAN SCHOOLS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the life of the school security guard in the context of “new normal” brought about by the global pandemic. As educational institutions adapt to the challenges of this unprecedented era, the role of school security guard has become increasingly vital in maintaining a safe and secure environment for students, staff, and visitors. The purpose of this study is to shed light on the unique challenges, responsibilities, and experiences faced by school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic. This research utilizes a qualitative approach, employing in-depth interview to gather data from school security guards rendering duties in the diocesan school. The findings of this study highlight the multifaceted role played by school security guards during the pandemic. They serve as frontline workers, responsible for implementing and enforcing safety protocols, managing access control, and ensuring the well-being of students, staff, and visitors. The findings also reveal that school security guards have demonstrated remarkable adaptability and resilience in the face of the new normal. They have embraced their expanded responsibilities and successfully implemented health and safety protocols within their schools. It emphasizes the importance of collaboration and effective communication among all stakeholders involved in school security including school administrators, policy makers and local security agencies in developing comprehensive strategies to address the evolving security needs. The findings further underscore the significance of fostering a supportive and inclusive environment that prioritizes the well-being of school security guards and the entire school community.

Keywords: *school security guards, COVID-19 pandemic, experiences and challenges, qualitative research*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought unprecedented challenges to the education system, impacting the safety and well-being of students, teachers, and staff. Amidst these challenges, school security guards have played a crucial role in maintaining a safe and secure learning environment. This study aims to explore the experiences of the school security guards during the pandemic, shedding light on their functions, duties, and responsibilities and recognizing their invaluable contributions. In educational environments, the indispensable yet non-teaching staff members' experiences are frequently disregarded. The insights that may be gleaned from examining the experiences of security guards can influence the decisions that are made about policy at educational institutions and lead to improved preparedness for future emergencies. Having a better understanding of what worked successfully and where adjustments are needed can be helpful in developing more thorough plans for responding to emergencies.

School security guards serve as the front-line defenders of school safety, taking on multifaceted roles that extend beyond traditional security measures. Their primary function is to ensure the safety and security of students, teachers, and staff within the school premises. This involves actively monitoring school grounds, promptly responding to security threats and emergencies, and maintaining order by enforcing rules and preventing crimes from occurring (Security Guard Training Central, 2019).

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, school security guards have assumed additional responsibilities to mitigate risks associated with COVID-19. They have become instrumental in implementing and enforcing COVID-19 safety protocols, such as mask-wearing, social distancing, and hand hygiene, to minimize the spread of the virus within the school community (Reesor, 2021).

Moreover, school security guards are actively involved in conducting health screening, including temperature checks and health assessments, to ensure a safe and secure learning environment. They play a pivotal role in ensuring the seamless continuation of the teaching-learning process and the uninterrupted operation of the school during the COVID-19 pandemic. Their diligent performance of duties is crucial in maintaining an environment conducive to learning and in effectively managing gate tensions arising from COVID-19 restrictions. Recognizing their contribution is essential as it directly impacts the continuity of education and helps in navigating the challenges posed by the pandemic's constraints.

Background of the Study

A security guard is a private citizen employed by individuals and organizations to protect the life of their employer's staff, clients, and property (Charles, 2020). They are the key persons in maintaining peace and order. Charles (2020) further reiterated that the life of a security guard is especially concerned with being the eyes and ears of an organization, such that it is protected from theft, vandalism, shady behavior, or illegal activities.

Singh (2019) stated that security guards have various duties and responsibilities. They are responsible for monitoring school grounds, enforcing school policies, and responding to emergencies. They work closely with school administrators, teachers, and local law enforcers to ensure the safety and well-being of everyone on campus. They forestall and deter crime and enforce the rules and regulations where they are guarding. They made sure to secure all properties under their jurisdiction and ensure that all these assets and properties of the company are safe and intact even during a temporary closure, to ensure that the company can immediately return to normal operations once the office doors open once again (Reesor, 2021). Hence, the duty of a school security guard is really full of challenges.

Shpeizer (2021) stated that security in educational institutions has distinctive structural characteristics, considering the population to be protected and the roles, activities, and goals of these institutions. The bigger the area the wider the scope of their responsibility to provide the security of their jurisdiction. Barton (2016) states that a security guard's main focus is to diffuse potentially violent situations wherever they may be, as well as notice anything suspicious that could cause others or the company some sort of harm.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant effect on the lives of school security guards. The pandemic forced school security guards to adapt to new roles and responsibilities, such as monitoring virtual learning platforms and ensuring students followed online safety guidelines. There are also added responsibilities on top of their usual routines of work. Implementing new safety protocols, enforcing social distancing, and dealing with non-compliant students and staff can be highly stressful and challenging. This requires a constant state of vigilance, the ability to remain calm under pressure, and a willingness to put oneself in harm's way to protect others.

According to an article published by CNN Philippines in August 2020, school security guards in the Philippines have faced several challenges during the pandemic. One guard described feeling anxious about the risk of exposure to the virus, while others expressed concerns about the lack of protective gear and training. Many guards reported feeling overworked, as they were required to perform additional duties without receiving additional compensation.

Tansely (2021) stated that being a security officer can often mean long shifts, night work, rushed meals, little movement, and poor work-life balance, leading to an effect on mental health and well-being. During the pandemic, many security guards had to work longer hours. They had to work more extended shifts and sometimes without break. Nair and Thusoo (2021) reiterated in their study that the COVID-19 pandemic had a devastating impact on all sections of society but has disproportionately hurt marginalized communities. They further emphasized that many have suffered from loss of livelihoods and lack of access to food, shelter, healthcare, and other basic needs. One of the issues that has affected school security guards in the Philippines during the pandemic is the closure of schools. Many schools have been laid off or placed on indefinite leave due to the closure of schools, which has had a significant impact on their livelihoods (www.cnnphilippines.com/news/2020/8/13/school-security-guards).

The COVID-19 pandemic increased hazards for security guards. They continued to work even during the pandemic, which increased their risk of coronavirus exposure. Their risk of getting infected with the virus is high while trying to maintain the safety of the public (www.securitytoday.com). Moreover, security guard during the pandemic is more exposed to aggressive people who were resistant following the COVID-19 pandemic, which put them at risk of harm. Nair and Thusoo (2021) stated that the job of security guards during the pandemic is riskier than ever.

Private security guards are the front liners in maintaining COVID-19 safety norms. According to Reesor (2021), "security guards have played a vital role as frontline workers amid COVID-19 pandemic". They always ensure that every person within a particular establishment has followed the safety procedures like hand-washing, social distancing, and wearing of masks. The demand for their work has tightened and become more complicated due to the sudden outbreak of the COVID-19 virus. The pandemic has created a stressful and uncertain environment for everyone involved in school, and school security guards are vigilant in ensuring that students and staff are safe both in-person and online (ABC News, August 2020).

School leaders ensure safety and an ideal environment for the faculty and staff, students, and their stakeholders. Securing the school makes the students and parents more comfortable (Wazile, 2018). According to Strauss (2020), school security measures can increase safety

among students and staff. According to the report by the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2020), visible security measures help deter potential threats and reduce fear and anxiety. School security guards played a crucial role in providing this security support.

For these reasons, school leaders also need to understand the life of these security guards to ensure a safe and productive school operation. This study explores the experiences of the school security guards during the pandemic to better understand the life of these frontline workers. Understanding the life of these school security guards would also help school leaders identify some ways for security guards to fully achieve their duties and responsibilities and enable them to come up with policies and practices for the improvement of our educational operation.

Research Questions

The study aimed to understand the experiences of school security guards during the new normal, particularly their role in serving private schools during the pandemic, to shed light on their unique challenges, responsibilities, and overall experiences during this unprecedented time.

Further, this study sought to answer this central question: “How do the school security guards describe their experiences serving catholic schools during the COVID-19 pandemic?” In examining the central question, the following sub-questions will be explored:

1. What were the experiences of a school security guard during the COVID-19 pandemic?
2. How did they adapt to the evolving demands of their role during the pandemic?
3. What challenges did they face in ensuring the implementation of safety protocols?
4. What coping strategies did they employ to address the emotional and psychological impact of the crisis?
5. What values can be extracted from the experiences of school security in the new normal?

METHODOLOGY

Research Method

This research adopted a qualitative case study approach to gain an in-depth understanding of the experiences of school security guards during the pandemic. The case study design allows for exploring specific cases (schools) and collecting rich, detailed data to address the research questions effectively.

Data Collection Method

The Researcher used the case study research method to understand the experiences of the school security guards assigned in the catholic school during the new normal. The researcher performed the following methods in collecting the data:

- a. Semi-structured interview. Individual semi-structured interviews were conducted with the school security guards. The interviews focused on their experiences, challenges faced, strategies employed, and the support received during the pandemic. The

interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

- b. Document Analysis: Review relevant documents such as school policies and health and safety protocols to gain additional insights into the role of security guards during the pandemic.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the five diocesan schools in the diocese of Dipolog City Zamboanga del Norte, namely, Saint Vincent's College, Inc. Dipolog City, St. Joseph College of Sindangan, Inc., St. Estanilao Kostka College, Inc. of Manukan, Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan City, Inc., and Colegio de San Francisco Javier of Rizal, Zamboanga del Norte, Inc. This study was performed in the 2021-2022 school year.

Research Participants

The research participants in this study were the selected school security guards assigned to the five diocesan schools in the diocese of Dipolog during the COVID-19 pandemic. A purposive sampling technique was employed in selecting the participants for this study. Participants who have been actively involved in managing security concerns during the COVID-19 pandemic are selected. The selection criteria include their roles, years of experience, and level of involvement in implementing safety protocols. Purposeful sampling ensures that the participants have relevant experiences and insights to contribute to the research questions to ensure the inclusion of various perspectives and experiences of school security guards during the pandemic.

Additionally, the researcher includes selected school administrators, faculty, and students as additional participants to provide a broader context and enhance the understanding of the experiences of school security guards.

Sampling Technique

Guided by the case study model of Merriam (1998), a purposive sampling technique was used in this study to select participants who have served as school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic. The selection criteria prioritize guards with diverse backgrounds, experiences, and perspectives to capture a range of insights. The sample size is determined by data saturation, where new information ceases to emerge. This study used purposive sampling to ensure detailed and relevant information about the phenomenon.

Purposive sampling is a non-random sampling method where participants are selected based on specific criteria that align with the research objectives. In this case, the researchers purposefully selected school security guards who served during the COVID-19 pandemic, aiming to capture diverse experiences, perspectives, and backgrounds.

The criteria for participant selection include factors such as the length of service, roles, and responsibilities during the pandemic, and willingness to share their experiences. By selecting participants who have firsthand experience working as school security guards during the pandemic, the researchers can gain valuable insights into the unique challenges, adaptations, and coping strategies employed in their roles.

Purposive sampling allows for targeted participant selection, ensuring that the sample includes individuals with the necessary knowledge and experiences to provide valuable insights related to the research questions. The researchers can gather in-depth and rich data relevant to the study objectives by selecting participants based on specific criteria.

However, it is important to acknowledge that purposive sampling may introduce some bias, as the participants are not randomly selected from the entire population. Therefore, the generalizability of the findings to the broader population of school security guards may be limited. Nonetheless, this study focuses on capturing the experiences and perspectives of the selected participants, providing a comprehensive understanding of the specific context of school security during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Additionally, the researcher included selected school administrators, faculty, and students as additional participants to provide a broader context and enhance the understanding of the experiences of school security guards. These participants provided different perspectives on the roles and interactions of security guards within the school community during the pandemic. Further, the responses of these additional participants helped validate the data provided by the school security guards.

Research Instrument

The researcher was the main instrument in this study, guided by the interview protocols. This approach is commonly known as the "researcher as the instrument," recognizing that the researcher played a vital role in gathering, interpreting, and analyzing the qualitative data.

The researcher conducted one-on-one interviews with the school security guards, allowing them to share their experiences, perceptions, and challenges in their own words. The researcher employed active listening and probing techniques to elicit in-depth responses.

Throughout the data collection activities, the researcher's role extended beyond simply asking questions and doing observations on the security guards. The researcher actively engaged with the participants by building rapport and creating a safe and trusting environment for open and honest sharing.

During the interview, the researcher-maintained reflexivity and acknowledged her biases, assumptions, and potential influence on the data collection process. Reflexivity involves self-awareness and critical reflection on how the researcher's background, beliefs, and experiences may shape the research interactions and interpretations.

Data Gathering Procedure

A qualitative case study researcher needs to acquire the necessary skills and follow certain data-gathering procedures. Using the case study model of Merriam (1998), the researcher conducted effective interviews and carefully observed the participants to enhance deeper understanding.

The researcher follows the following procedures in gathering the necessary data: a.) Identify participants using purposive sampling, b.) obtain necessary approvals from the President of the Diocesan Schools and Vice President for Administration, c.) Distribute informed consent to the selected participants, d.) Schedule appointments and venue for the interview, and e.) Conduct the interview.

Before the data collection, the researcher observed some ethical standards and protocols, such as seeking necessary approvals for the interview and distributing informed consent. Guided by the theories of Wa-Mbaleka and Rosario (2022) for data collection procedures in qualitative

research, the researcher performed the following procedure to obtain the necessary data for this research study.

Figure 1. Data Collection process

Figure 1 illustrates the data collection procedures involved in this study. Before the data were collected, the researcher sought approval from the President of the diocesan schools to interview two security guards from each diocesan school. Once approved, the researcher asked permission from the vice president for administration of every district school to interview the selected school security guards. Before setting a schedule for the interview, informed consent was distributed to each participant, carefully stating the aim or purpose of conducting the private interview and reassuring them of confidentiality and anonymity. Then, the schedule for the in-depth interview is set preferably during their off-duties to avoid obstructing their school duties and responsibilities.

Merriam (1998) perceives qualitative case study as “an intensive, holistic description and analysis of a bounded phenomenon such as a program, an institution, a person, a process, or a social unit” (p. xiii).

She described a qualitative study with unique, distinctive attributes: Particularistic (it focuses on the situation, event, program, or phenomenon); Descriptive (it yields a detailed, thick description of the phenomenon under study); Heuristic (it illuminates the reader’s understanding of phenomenon under study) (Yazan, 2015).

To ensure a smooth interview process flow, a semi-structured interview guide was developed to provide a framework for the interview while allowing flexibility for participants to elaborate on their experiences and express their thoughts and emotions. The interview guide consisted of open-ended questions that aligned with the research objectives and explored topics such as adaptations to the pandemic, challenges faced, coping strategies employed, and values derived from the experiences.

Conducting the Interviews

The interviews were conducted in a private and comfortable setting that promotes open and honest communication. The researcher established rapport with the participants, creating a supportive environment for sharing their experiences. During the interviews, the researcher

asked the questions from the guide and encouraged participants to elaborate on their responses. Probing questions were used to delve deeper into specific aspects of their experiences.

With the participants' consent, the interviews were audio-recorded to ensure the accurate capturing of their responses and to facilitate data transcription.

Observing the participants

In addition to audio recording, the researcher took detailed notes during the interviews, documenting non-verbal cues, observations, and any other relevant information that enhances the understanding of the participants' experiences.

The research tool used in this study was semi-structured interviews. Qualitative data collection methods are exploratory and allow rich and thick descriptions of people's life experiences in a very certain phenomenon while making sense of their behavior (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Merriam, 2009). With this idea, the researcher used an in-depth interview to gather the mandatory data.

After the interview was conducted, the researcher started transcribing the interview transcripts. Interview transcripts refer to transcribing the interview from an oral to a written mode and structuring the conversation in a form amenable to closer analysis (Kvale, 2018, p.98). These interview transcripts were then member-checked (Appendix A) for validation and accuracy. After it had been checked, the data collected were analyzed using the phenomenological method of bracketing and reduction. This involves setting aside preconceptions and biases to focus on the essence of the experience and reducing the data to its essential structure.

De Guzman and Gaikwad (2022) stated in their study that research interview could be a social engagement or a “conversational partnership” (Rubin & Rubin, 2012, p. 7) “to understand the planet from the subjects’ point of view, . . . and uncover the meaning of their experience” (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2015, p. 5). Brinkmann and Kvale (2018) state that the interviewer has the scientific competence to initiate and interact with the interviewee to gain knowledge during the interaction. He or she directs the interview topic, inquiries to ask, answers to follow up, and culminates the conversation. The tactic of questioning employs descriptive and structural questioning additionally a novel use of imaginative variation to explore experience (Teban, 2014).

This study used purposive or subjective sampling techniques in selecting the participants. This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups who are especially experienced or experienced with the phenomenon of interest (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In step with Patton (2007), Purposive sampling is a sampling technique that permits the choice of people (or sites) who are knowledgeable of the phenomenon under investigation. Creswell and Poth (2018) describe them as the most informed people on the problem. During this study, participants are selected to support their service before and through the pandemic to confirm satisfactory information for the research.

Data Management

Data management is the most important initial step of data analysis (Merriam, 1998). Data analysis is made more convenient when data is well-organized, whether done manually or computer-assisted data analysis (Wa-Mbaleka & Araceli, 2022). The researcher used both software and manual data management methods. The researcher used Hyper *Research version 4.5.3* to manage the data. With the use of this tool, coding significant quotes from the participants

was made easier. Since it was just a trial version of hyperresearch, which can only accommodate up to 50 codes, the researcher also applied manual data management using Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel to combine the codes generated from the hyperresearch.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is “the process of making sense out of the data... [which] involves consolidating, reducing, and interpreting what people have said and what the researcher has seen and read – it is the process of making meaning” (Merriam,1998).

The data analysis in the qualitative study involves a systematic process of organizing, coding, interpreting, and synthesizing the collected data to derive meaningful insights and answer the research questions. The analysis aims to identify patterns, themes, and connections within the data, providing a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Transcription and Familiarization: The audio recordings of the interviews with school security guards, as well as any additional interviews conducted with administrators, faculty, and students, are transcribed verbatim. The researcher familiarizes the data by repeatedly reading and listening to the transcripts, gaining a holistic understanding of the content and context of the interviews. In analyzing and interpreting the information, the researcher applied the thematic analysis. Thematic analysis begins with coding the information about assigning legs for your data (Adu, 2016). To confirm and capture the core meaning of the phenomenon is to research the information in bits to form a sense of it (De Guzman, 2022).

Coding: The researchers engage in an iterative process of coding the data. Initially, open coding is employed, where significant statements, phrases, or concepts are identified and labeled with descriptive codes. This process allows for exploring various perspectives and themes that emerge from the data. Related codes are grouped into categories as coding progresses, forming broader themes that encapsulate the participants' experiences.

Theme Development: The researcher analyzed the coded data to identify recurring patterns and themes. She looked for similarities, differences, and connections within and across the interviews. Themes are developed based on the frequency, relevance, and significance of the codes within the dataset. The significant statements from the transcripts were used to identify themes (Creswell, 2013; Moustakas, 1994). The theme refers to a frequently used word or phrase (van Manen, 1990). To fully describe the phenomenon, a discovery of themes emerges from the common codes from the significant statements of the participant's responses added to the rich, descriptive analysis. Common codes were then clustered together to create a theme. These themes fully describe the phenomenon. These themes capture the main findings and provide a coherent structure to organize and present the study results.

Interpretation and Synthesis: The researcher interprets the themes of the research questions and the existing literature. The researcher examines the relationships between the themes, exploring the underlying meanings and implications of the participants' experiences. The researcher aims to generate a rich and nuanced interpretation of the data, capturing the complexities and nuances of the school security guards' experiences during the pandemic.

Triangulation: To provide a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of school security guards and confirmation of the main participant's responses, additional information was gathered through interviews with selected school administrators, faculty, and students. These interviews offered diverse perspectives on the roles and interactions of security guards within the school community during the pandemic.

Validation and Member Checking: Aside from triangulation to validate the participant's responses, the researcher sought validation and member-checking by sharing the preliminary

findings with the participants or other experts in the field. This process allows participants to review and confirm the accuracy and representation of their experiences, adding credibility and trustworthiness to the analysis. Thoughtful and purposeful member checking ensured the transcriptions were accurate and consistent (Moustakas, 1994). This was a very important part of the study. Member checking in this study was done by returning the data to the participants. This allowed participants to check for accuracy and added to the credibility of the experience (Creswell, 2013). Member-checking is the most crucial technique to establish credibility (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Wa-Mbaleka & Rosario, 2022).

Reporting: The findings of the analysis are synthesized and presented clearly and coherently. The researchers provide detailed descriptions and supporting evidence for each theme, incorporating relevant quotes and interview examples. The analysis is contextualized within the existing literature and research framework, contributing to the broader understanding of the topic.

By employing rigorous data analysis procedures, this study ensures that the insights derived from the participants' experiences are grounded in the data and supported by evidence. The analysis process allows for a thorough exploration of the research questions, offering valuable insights into the experiences of school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic. In analyzing and interpreting the information, the researcher applied the thematic analysis. The thematic analysis begins with coding the information about assigning tags for your data (Adu, 2016). To confirm and capture the core meaning of the phenomenon is to research the information in bits to form a sense of it (De Guzman, 2022).

RESULTS

The findings are presented systematically, followed by a detailed analysis and interpretation of the data. Merriam, 1998 pointed out that data analysis is not concluded when data collection is completed. Instead, analysis becomes more intensive as the study progresses.

Based on the analysis of the interview transcripts of the school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic, prominent themes emerged that encapsulated the experiences of school security guards during the pandemic. The themes that arose were categorized into security guard experiences, challenges, and coping strategies. Three themes emerged in the experiences of the school security guards, namely: a) *Adapting to new Responsibilities*, b) *Monitoring and Securing Safety at all costs*, and c) *Feeling Proud Front Liners Amidst Risk*.

Other five (5) themes under the challenges of the school security guards during the pandemic namely: a) Defiance of the protocol, b) Disrespectful clients, c) Miscommunication with peers and workmates, d) Deficient time for family, and e) Difficulty in Adapting to new demands.

Another four (4) themes emerged for their coping strategies to meet the evolving demands and mitigate emotional and psychological crises brought on by the pandemic. These themes are: a) *Understanding vital role*, b) *Sticking to policy to ensure safety*, c) *Fostering a sense of collaboration*, and d) *Seeking support and maintaining open communication*.

These themes are derived from the interview transcripts of the participants based on the four sub-questions to saturate necessary information and provide an answer to the focus question, which further describes the experiences of the school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic. The participant's responses to the interview questions are considered personal accounts of their respective experiences. The themes that emerged from the participants' accounts were presented and organized according to the sub-questions stated in the statement of the problem of this study. Some themes have corresponding sub-themes, while others don't have any distinctive sub-themes. Short quoted statements from the interview

transcripts are also provided. English translations were provided in brackets following the original statements of the participants.

Experiences of a school security guard during the Covid-19 pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the education sector, forcing schools to implement various safety measures to protect students, staff, and visitors. The school security guards are at the forefront of ensuring security and safety. This research theme delves into the unique experiences and challenges faced by school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of their roles, responsibilities, and the impact of the pandemic on their professional and personal lives.

Adapting to new Responsibilities. Participants discussed the significant shift in their duties, with a heightened focus on enforcing COVID-19 safety measures. They reported an increased emphasis on enforcing COVID-19 safety measures, such as monitoring mask usage, social distancing, and temperature checks. This theme highlights their ability to quickly adapt and respond to the evolving demands of their role to ensure the safety and well-being of the school community. Data from the interviews revealed that school security guards experienced significant shifts in their responsibilities and protocols due to the pandemic. This shift required them to adapt their routines and prioritize public health protocols alongside their traditional security duties. Participants initially felt overwhelmed but gradually adapted to their new roles.

“... dili gyud malimod nga nabag-ohan gyud ko maam kay lahi ra man gyud sa naandan. Pero karon okey na kay nakaadyas naman pud maam”. [... it can't be denied that we are overwhelmed on the sudden change but later we had able to adjust unto it]. SG2 said.

School security guards faced a significant shift in their responsibilities during the pandemic, with an increased focus on enforcing health and safety protocols. They faced challenges in monitoring social distancing, mask-wearing, and sanitization measures. They had to adapt quickly to new protocols while ensuring compliance among students and staff, which is far from what they traditionally do. Adapting Security Protocols and Procedures is not difficult, but implementing them is not easy, according to SP1.

“... Dili mn problema ang pag adopt sa mga kabag-ohan maam pero ang pag-implementar maoy lisod tungod kay dili mn tanan mosunod.” [... adopting the new protocols is not a problem, but it's on the implementation of the said protocols that becomes more difficult since not everyone is compliant unto it] SP1 said.

Another participant gave a similar statement when they were asked about their experience on the implementation of the COVID-19 protocols:

“...una, medyo nagkalisod gyud ug adyas kay nabag-ohan man, pero kadugayan naanad na”. [... at first, most of our clients had difficulty adjusting, particularly in the strict implementation of the protocols, but later, since it is already part of the new normal, they could adjust to it]. SG5 said.

Certain task can be very difficult especially if we are not used unto it, this was felt by these security guards:

“...nabag-ohan gyud ko maam sa mga protocol mao nga medyo lisod gyud kay lahi ra man gyud kaayo tungod kay bag-o naman pud ang pamaagi”. [the protocol is new to us that’s why we find it so difficult because we are not really used to it]. said SG7.

“...dili gyud malikayan nga magkaliboglibog ma’am (pause for a while then shook his head) bale bitaw to maam, labina kon magduot ang mga kliyente. Mabalaw lagi mi ug pamad-long. Pero sa kadugayan maanad naman pud. Sa sugod lang gyud medyo lisod bisan ug nakaagi sa trining. [at first, we cannot avoid the feeling of being confused even we are trained already especially if there are already many clients. That’s why we really have to admonish them to observe the protocols] said SG 9.

Most participants have shared similar experiences in the implementation of the COVID-19 protocols.

The pandemic has altered their roles and expanded their responsibilities in enforcing the health and safety protocols, such as mask-wearing, social distancing, and hygiene practices. This theme highlights the increased responsibilities shouldered by school security guards in enforcing COVID-19 safety protocols.

Feeling Proud Front Liners amidst Risk. School security guards felt blest and proud as a front liner. According to them, it was the most unique experience that they ever encountered in their life. Though risky, it was also very fulfilling for a security guard to be a front liner. They monitored body temperature and stood as standby health and safety implementers in school at the height of the pandemic. They assessed the existing security protocols and procedures in schools and ensured the effectiveness in mitigating risks associated with the pandemic.

“.. nindot gyud paminawon maam pero medyo kulba usab tungod kay peligro man sab kay naa man ta sa panahon sa pandemya. Pwede nga matakdan gyud dayon kon simbako infected and kliyente,mao nga salig nalang gyud sa kahitas an maam”. [to be a font liner sounds great, but our safety is at risk since it is at the time of the pandemic. The possibility to be infected is always present especially if we accommodated a positive client. That’s why we just rely our safety to God] said SG2.

According to them, being a first-time front-liner is not easy. It’s just like when you are given a task you are not used to. The feeling of uneasiness and hesitation embodied.

“...usahay makulbaan ko maam labina kon moaksyon ug taas ang Temperature kay kuyaw gyud mao ako daun iusob ug temperityur tsik. Maau kon normal ra pero kon medyo taas, ibutang gyud sila sa obserbasyon desk.”[... sometimes I’m tensed especially if the temperature is high so I recheck it. It’s ok if it’s normal temperature but if not I

really send the client to the observation desk for monitoring purposes].
SG 3 added.

SG4 emphasized his experience of being a front liner:

“... Pormero ma’am medyo mahadlok ko mokuha ug temperature kay unya dili mao pero naningkamot gyud ko nga makahibalo kay mao naman ang kabag-ohan. Sa kanunay pagbalikbalik nakakat-on r gyud. dali ra man pud kat-onon. Pero dili malikayan ang kakulba nga masayop, basta pursigido lang gyud nga makahibalo. [...at first, it seemed that I am really cautious to check the temperature because I am afraid to commit mistakes but I really try my best to learn as long as you are willing learn you can easily do it] SG4 confessed.

In this field of work the participant’s own safety was already set aside. According them, they are no longer thinking for their own safety but they already focused on their duties and responsibilities as front liners at that time. This is proven by SG6 in his statement:

“... sa panahon nga dunay magpakita ug symptoms mao gyud ang pinakakulba maam, tungod kay pamilyado gud mi unsaon nalang kon matakdan mi,pero tungod kay trabaho man, mao amo gyud gipaningkamutang buhaton ug unsa ang angay namo himuon para sa kaayuhan sa tanan.Tungod kay possible sa gamay namong sayup, daghan ang maapektuhan. Mao nga bantay gyud pirmi sa trabaho as frontliner.[...the most critical part ma’am is when someone shows a symptom of the virus infection. We are really worried because we are also family persons. We are thinking on the safety of our family, since it is part of our job, we do it to the best of our capacity for the benefit of everyone, because one small failure might harm everyone, that’s why we really do our best as frontliner] added SG6.

SG8 also affirmed:

“.... Usa gyud ni sa pinakanindot nga bahin sa trabaho maam bisan kuyaw pro nindot man paminawon nga makatabang ta sa kadaghanan. Kutob sa among mahimo himuon gyud para sa siguridad sa kadaghanan . Dapat abtik, ligdong ug naay baruganan kay kon masayup mi niadtong panahon sa pandemic daghan man ang maapektuhan mao nga pokus gyud sa trabaho. [... being a front liner is one of the best part of our job, even it was so risky but it is so satistying to hear that you are helping everyone. We do everything we can for the safety of everyone. During that time, we should always be smart, and firm on our decisions because one small mistake might harm everyone] SG8 explained.

Another participant also has similar experiences as them. Most of them commented that their experience as a front liner was fulfilling and unforgettable. Though the task was tough, it was worthwhile.

Monitoring and Securing Safety at all costs. Identifying areas for improvement and adaptation of security measures, such as access control, surveillance systems, and emergency response plans, to align with the changing safety landscape are the sole objectives of these security guards. They always keep and ensure their posts' safety at all times. This is shown in their statement:

“...dili lang ang pag implementar sa standard protocols and among pokus maam apil ghaon ang kinatibuk ang septi sa among post. Kanunay gyud namong i-check ang palibot. Kumbaga, safety and security sa among post gyud ang dapat mauna.[... our focus is not only on the implementation of the standard protocols but also the safety and security of our post. We always check our surroundings. We are prioritizing the safety and security of our post.]SG8, said.

“... sa pagsugod gyud sa among shift kinahanglan gyud nga among i-tsik ang erya maam. Daun pagkahuman sa among shift amo ghaon subayan ug usob usa mi mobiya. [... it is important that we have to check first the area before we start and end our shift]. Added SG 10.

Each assigned security guard has to perform his duties and responsibilities. Most of them have similar statements in terms of monitoring the safety and security of their post.

“.. sa panahon sa pandemya dili mas relax ang roving gard sa gabii kay mingaw man, lahi r sa walay pandemya. Pero mas bisi kon giter (gate in-charge) maam kay daghan man bantayan sama sa mga protocols. [...during the pandemic roving guard is more relax than the gate in-charge because we have so many things to consider upon entrance just like the protocols], said SG9.

“... kon maasayn sa gate kinahanglan gyud nga hugot ipatuman ang mga protocol kay responsibilidad man gyud namo kon naay makasulod nga pasitib sa bayrus mao nga todo bantay gyud, ma'am.[... when assigned as gate in-charge, it is really important to strictly implement the protocols because it is our responsibility when somebody entered the campus positive with the virus.], elaborated SG9.

Challenges Faced in Ensuring the Implementation of Safety Protocols

The COVID-19 pandemic necessitated the implementation of rigorous safety protocols within educational institutions to protect students, staff, and visitors. School security guards played a vital role in enforcing these protocols. This research theme focuses on the challenges school security guards encounter in ensuring the effective implementation of safety protocols during the pandemic. By identifying and understanding these hurdles, this research aims to contribute to developing strategies and solutions that can facilitate successful protocol implementation and enhance overall safety within schools.

Participants discussed difficulties enforcing mask usage and social distancing, particularly among younger students who found it challenging to adhere to these guidelines consistently. They also mentioned resistance or pushback from some students, staff, or parents who questioned the necessity of the protocols. Limited resources, such as personal protective equipment (PPE) or sanitization supplies, were highlighted as obstacles to effectively carrying out their responsibilities. This theme underscores the importance of addressing these challenges and providing the necessary support to implement safety measures successfully. *Defiance to the protocol, Disrespectful clients, Miscommunication with peers and workmates, Deficient time for family, and Difficulty Adapting to new demands* were identified as key challenges. Security guards had to navigate these challenges while prioritizing the safety and well-being of the school community.

Defiance to the protocol. It cannot be denied that despite the repeated delivery of information requiring everyone to follow and perform the health protocols, not everyone is compliant. They often encountered resistance from students and staff who were not fully compliant with wearing masks or following other safety measures. There are still those who are resistant to the policies even if they cause risk to their life. Participants reported being subject to complaints and aggressive behaviors, especially those not compliant with the policies. Not only the parents but students as well.

“..... *bisan na kapila balikbalikon nga magdala ug ballpen kon magkuhaug module kay dili pwee maghulamhulam, apan wala lang ghapon* “. [... even they are informed repeatedly about no borrowing of ballpens during the claiming of the modules, still nothing happens.] SG7.

Security guards reported difficulties managing large gatherings or events while maintaining proper distancing and crowd control. Sometimes, due to these non-compliant clients, it tested their temperament that likely led to light arguments.

“.... *Naa gyud usahay maam nga magkabingkil tungod sa pagpatuman sa protocol pero masettle r mn dayon*”. [... There are times that arguments arise due to the implementation of the protocols but later on it will be settled]. SG 3.

Even students can attest to how those non-compliant individuals reacted to the implementation of protocols. However, since security guards have to adhere to strict implementation.

“..... *sometimes light arguments arise in implementing the protocols because, as security guards, they ensure that everyone has followed, pero bisan unsaon moinsist man gyud*

ang uban mao magsumpaki daun.” HSS01.

Faculty participants and even students attested that some parents and students did not adhere to the existing COVID-19 health and safety protocols. One teacher said:

“... Although we repeatedly orient the parents on the existing health and safety protocols, not everyone can follow.” F01

Participants in the study also reported the following challenges they encountered. Most of them claimed to be subject to complaints from most students and parents, especially in implementing the protocols. According to them, it's not easy to implement new policies because people find it so hard to adopt. Considering the sudden change of some practices, there are individuals who cannot directly adopt the new policies, which results in complaints or rejections. SG 10 shared:

“ ...Tungod kay higpit gyud sa pagpatuman ngadto sa mga estudyante ang mga protocolos sama sa temperature check, logbook, alcohol mao nga dili malikayan nga mocomplain gyud sila labina kon magdalidali n sa klase”. [...Due to our strict implementation of the health and safety protocols like temperature checking, logbook, disinfection (alcohol) and hand washing before they will be admitted, it cannot be avoided that students and parents really complain especially if they are late already or they are in a hurry.]. SG10.

Disrespectful clients. Aside from complaints, they also encounter behavioral problems for some students. There are students who love to break rules or seek attention, which adds to the burden of the responsibilities of these security guards. According to them, sometimes they also encounter disrespectful students who often break rules and policies in school. One security guard shared his sentiments in his post:

“...Usahay kami ra bantayan sa mga estudyante labina kay single post mi mao dili kaau namo mabantayan ang mga estudyante sa sulod k kinahanglan man gyud atangan ang gate. Mabantayan nalang namo maam nga naan a diay damages to some school facilities sama sa giguba na ang gripo kon walay tubig o dili ba kha, biyaan ang gripo nga nakaabri”. [...Sometimes students just take advantage on us especially that when we are in single post, ‘gater’ (means in-charge of the entrance and exits) at the same time roving guard’, that’s the reason we cannot really attend to some student’s behavior inside the campus, later we just found out that there are already damages to some school facilities like broken faucet if there are no water or simply leaving the faucet open]. SG6.

Another participants also shared his sentiments in his post:

“... naay panahon maam nga maglisod gali mi maam ug excuse bisan sa pagpangihing dili man mabiyaan ang among post kay single post man mi maam. Mao hulaton lng gyud namo nga dili na kaayo busy usa pa daun makaresponse sa personal call”. [...there were times that we cannot even response to personal call of nature, we will just wait when it is no longer our busy schedule

before we can do our personal necessities]. SG7.

The issue of behavioral problems was common to other schools. But they just vary depending on the needs and type of students. Other guards had experienced disrespect among students and clients. Due to the restrictions and protocols caused by the pandemic, security guards have to be firm in implementing the policies, but not everyone wholeheartedly follows.

“... naay uban maam nga molikay labina kon maatul nga Daghang kliyente. Daun kon imo sirbatuhan moingon lang nga mo-balik ra daun.[... there are some who never submit themselves for inspection, especially if it is already crowded, and when caught they will just likely say that they will be back right away.]explained SG5.

“... Naa pay uban nga masuko kay galangan-langan ra kay tua permanente na sila ug sulod gawas ngano balikbalikon pa ug tsik. [... others also get angry when checked because for them, it's just a waste of time since they are always going in and out the campus]. Added SG4.

Most of them had shared similar sentiments regarding their difficulties in implementing the COVID-19 protocols. There are avid followers of the standard health and safety protocols, but there are also those who are hard-headed and fun of disobeying the rules.

Deficient time for family. Their time for the family has also been affected, especially if it is their duty shift. Due to the restrictions, their usual family routines change. If they usually had a family outing during their day off, during the pandemic, outing is already restricted; time for their family has been affected.

“... Medyo affected gyud maam, sama pananglit sa panahon nga naquarantine ko tungod kay naa man employee nga symptomatic, wala gyud ko kauli maam “. [... it was really affected maam, just when I was quarantined because there was an employee manifesting the COVID-19 symptoms, so I was not able to go home]. SG3

A similar incident was shared by SG 2; in his case, he voluntarily preferred not to go home during the height of COVID-19 just for his family's safety.

“... nagself- quarantine gyud ko diri sa school maam ka mahadlok mn ko nga maapektuhan ang akong pamilya ug akong trabaho mao nga wala nalang ko nag-ulian, ug diri sa ko school nagpirmi”. [... I really had self-quarantine here in school because I'm worried about my family and also my job, that's why I prefer to stay here in school]. SG2.

The pandemic has also affected some of their family routines. Due to the pandemic, and because of hectic schedules of work, they have limited time for family bonding, others none at all, especially that they also consider their safety. Unlike before the pandemic, they have allocated time for family bonding, preferably during their day. Most participants emphasized that as COVID-19 struck the country, their duties and responsibilities have tightened, considering that everyone must observe so many protocols and restrictions. Their time for family bonding has been affected. One of the security guards stated:

“.....Dili gyud ta makadalidali ug tanda sa atong mga ginikanan or makadalidali ug tapok or outing because of our busy schedules in our duties and there are also restrictions”. [...We cannot easily pay visits to our folks or do some family gatherings due to our busy schedules and aside from that, there are also restrictions]. SG5

Others have similar statements to this, emphasizing a limited time for family gatherings.

Miscommunication with peers and workmates. The worst experience they had during the pandemic was when they encountered avoidance even from their closest person, especially when they just had simple coughs. Others would likely think that it is already a symptom of COVID. SG 4 shared:

“...Bisan unsa kasuod maam kon pananglit nagpakita ka ug symptoms, mopalayo gyud nmo maam or moingon gyud na ayaw paduol nako,”. [...Even how close you are, but when you manifest COVID-like symptoms, that person would likely keep away from you]. SG4

According to them, it is understood considering that everyone is after of our safety, and this is also expected in the time of the pandemic.

Due to restrictions and strict implementation of the standard protocols, the image of the school security guards becomes alienated. They encounter difficulty in fostering friendly image before the students and stakeholders.

“... Dili gyud malikayan nga maingnan mi nga istrikto, apan igo ra gyud mi nagpatuman sa balaud. Amo lang gyud gibuhad ug unsa ang among responsabilidad para sa kaayuhan sa tanan”. [... it cannot be avoided that they branded us as strict, but we are just implementing the policies. We are just doing our responsibilities for the benefits of everyone] SG8.

School security guards often find themselves balancing enforcing security measures and fostering a supportive and inclusive environment for students.

This challenge arises from the need to create a safe space without creating an atmosphere of fear or intimidation.

“... ingon ani na gyud among image maam, kon unsa among gipanumpaon dapat amo gyud na barugan”.[... this is

our image ma'am. What we had sworn, we have to stand by it] SG 7.

Dealing with emergencies and potential threats is a significant aspect of a security guard's role. They respond promptly and effectively to various situations, such as intruders, fights, or medical emergencies. This responsibility places immense pressure on security guards, as their actions can directly impact the safety and well-being of those within the school community.

"... Ang safety sa among post maoy among priority maam".
[... the safety of our post is our priority maam] SG 6.

Most of the security guards agreed to this. They are undoubtedly called front liners because they work in the front line. They are not afraid to take risks. The security guards their selves are only second in priority; it's their post that is the priority.

Difficulty in Adapting to the new demands. Participants spoke passionately about their role in ensuring the safety and well-being of the school community. They take pride in their work and the fulfillment they derive from making a positive impact during challenging times. This theme highlights the dedication and resilience of security guards in fulfilling their responsibilities and underscores the importance of recognizing and appreciating their contributions. The COVID-19 pandemic has presented school security guards with unprecedented challenges, forcing them to adapt rapidly to the changing demands of their roles. This research theme focuses on exploring the strategies and approaches employed by school security guards to adapt to the evolving demands during the pandemic. By understanding their experiences and identifying effective adaptive measures, this research aims to shed light on the resilience and resourcefulness demonstrated by security guards in maintaining a safe and secure environment within educational institutions.

The sudden shift of responsibilities due to implementing the COVID-19 safety protocols partly became a challenge to every security guard. Temperature checking, writing in the logbooks, implementing social distancing and disinfection protocols, and checking face masks and shields are some of the added responsibilities of most security guards. These added routines require knowledge and skills. They have no option. Instead, they have to implement it directly.

".. pirmiro, lisod pa gyud kaau maam kay nabag ohan pa mn gud unsaon paggamit sama sa temperature scanner, pero naam n pud mi training ug orientation mao guided pud mi maam. Kadugayan, naanad na ug dali na ang paghimo". [.. at first, it was difficult because we were not used to it, just like the temperature scanner, but we also underwent training and orientation, and later it became easier for us to perform]. SG 3.

The initial adaptations made by security guards to fulfill their roles while ensuring compliance with health guidelines and government regulations become challenging, but security guards show flexibility in adapting the new policies and guidelines. They aligned the existing security protocols and procedures with the pandemic's evolving demands.

"... kanunay gyud magmabinantayon kada naa mosulod sa eskwelahan. Kinahanglan nga ipatuman kanunay ang mga prototocold para sa safety sa kadaghanan sama sa temperature

checking, wearing of face mask and disinfecting". [... we are really vigilant always, maam everytime they enter the campus. We really implement the protocols for the safety of everyone like closely monitoring their temperature, checking face mask and disinfecting] SG 10 said.

The impact of the pandemic on the security landscape within schools and how security guards responded to address emerging risks and vulnerabilities become prevalent. Security guards become sensitive to the behavior of the individual getting inside the campus. They closely monitor them to ensure the safety of everyone.

"... kon naa magpakita ug symptoms sa COVID, amo gyud dayon ihatud sa isolation room ug ireport daun ang kaso sa RHU". [... if anyone manifesting the COVID-19 symptoms, we directly send them to the isolation room and directly report the case to the Local Health Unit] said SG 7.

".. una medyo hadlok paminawon kon naay magpakita ug symptom sa COVID pero tungod kay frontliner man amo gyud himuon ug unsay angay himuon. [.. at first, it seems frightening to hear someone manifesting the COVID-19 symptoms, but since we are front liners and it is our role so we really do what is right.] added SG10.

Similar feedback was given by the school faculty and students as well.

"...security guards perform their duties and responsibilities during the pandemic, that's why we feel safe and comfortable every time we get inside the campus even during the pandemic because our security guards are strict in the implementation of the protocols". CS2 said.

Coping Strategies to Mitigate the Emotional and Psychological Impact of the Crisis.

Security guards are responsible for maintaining physical security and building positive relationships with students, staff, and parents. This can involve serving as a mentor or a trusted adult figure, creating a sense of trust and respect within the school community. This theme explores the coping strategies employed by security guards to address the emotional and psychological impact of the crisis. Strategies such as seeking social support, engaging in self-care activities, utilizing stress management techniques, and seeking professional support were identified as effective ways to mitigate the impact of the crisis.

Sticking to policy to ensure safety. One of their coping strategies to ensure safety and security is the strict implementation of the standard health and safety protocols. According to them, their strict implementation of the standard protocol is for everyone's safety; it's not only the call of duty but more for everyone's safety. They reported heightened vigilance in monitoring student and staff adherence to social distancing.

"...para sa safety sa tanan amo gyud gipanghingusgan ang NO FACE MASK/FACE SHIELD NO ENTRY POLICY"[..for the safety of everyone we strictly implement the NO FACE MASK/FACE SHIELD NO ENTRY POLICY]. SG5 said.

Similar statement was given by another participant:

“...Stik gyud mi sa polisiya ma’am para sa kaayuhan sa tanan. Bisan pa ug unsa ka suod pero gikinahanglan ghaon ang insaktong pagpatuman sa balaod para sa seguridad sa tanan. Kay kon simbako naay infected nga makalusot tanan mn daun mahiming biktima. Mao nga mosubay gyud mi ug unsa ang balaod.”. SG5

“... Policy is policy, ma’am ug wala gyud exempted niini kay bisan usa ang mainfect sa virus, kitang tanan possibleng ma quarantine”. [... Policy is policy, and no one is exempted because if one is infected in this area, everyone must be quarantined], clarified SG6.

The rest of the participants gave similar feedback. They all apply what was stated in the standard protocols to ensure safety for everyone.

Seeking support and maintaining open communication. Participants discussed feeling heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and fear due to the uncertainty surrounding the virus and their potential exposure to it. They highlighted concerns about their health and the well-being of their families. The coping strategies mentioned included seeking colleague support, maintaining open communication with loved ones, and **engaging in self-care activities** such as exercise or mindfulness. This theme underscores the importance of addressing security guards' emotional and psychological well-being during challenging times.

“.. importante sad and communication maam. Kanunay nga makigcoordinate sa admin sama pananglit kon unsa man ang mga problemang mabantayan ireport daun aron malikayan ang paglala sa problema. [...communication is also important. Coordinate directly to the school problem whenever problems arise to address it right-away.] said SG8.

Another participant also supports this statement:

“... kon unsa man ang problema nga mabantayan diritso nga ireport sa admin o dili ba kaha sa mga teachers aron daun masulbad.[..whatever problems we notice, we directly raise them to the school admin or the teachers to solve it right away.] clarified SG6.

The rest of the participants gave similar feedback. They emphasized the significance of addressing issues and concerns directly to the school administration or personnel concerned to solve the problem directly.

Fostering a sense of collaboration. During the pandemic, security guards must foster a sense of collaboration within the school community, administrators, teachers, and students in response to the pandemic. As a gatekeeper and a front liner, strong coordination with the school community, especially with the school administrator, is another important matter to consider. One security guard reported that security guards ensure an open channel for effective information sharing and timely response involving security purposes. Leveraging the use of technology is another evolving demand in their roles during the pandemic. One participant narrated:

“... kinahanglan gyud nga among kat onan ang mga kabag-ohan sama sa pagamit og mga bag ong devices nga gikinanglan sa among trabaho sama sa radio, walkie-talkie aron dali ang pag-hatag ug impormasyon ug aron masiguro ang kaligtasan sa tanan”. [We really need to equip ourselves in the use of new technologies and devices like handset radio, walkie-talkie, etc. in order to perform our duties well for the benefit of every one] said SG 2.

“... naa pud namo maam ang kanunay nga pagtina-bangay. Kon naay kalisod among kauban dili gyud mi magdumili ug hatag ug tabang. Sama pananglit sa paggamit sa thermal scanner labina sa bag-o pa medyo magkalisod gyud. [...we always observe the sense of collaboration. We always extend our help to our workmates. Just like when they encounter difficulties in using some devices like thermal scanner because we are not really familiar to it]. SG7 added.

This statement was also supported by SG9:

“... sa panahon sa pandemya mas nadoble ang among concern sa among kauban. Bisan gamay nga ubo o sip-on tambagan gyud dayon sa pagpahulay o pagpanambal. [... during the pandemic our concern to others has doubled. Even it was just a mild cough and colds, we directly advise them to take their meds and have a rest.] said SG9.

Being in charge of the school's safety and security, a security guard needs to be observant and sensitive to students and staff's behavior and well-being during the pandemic. They must constantly coordinate with the school admin, faculty, and staff to comply with this. They must communicate regularly with colleagues to share experiences, concerns, and emotional support. They were so excited to share the different personalities who had marked their lives during the crying times or in times of difficulties. Most of the answers appear that the school administration always opened its door for them and never left them behind in times of need, followed the school teachers and other employees, and few answered that it was their co-security guard. One participant shared:

“... thankful pud kaayo mi maam kay very supportive man ang school admin ug mga faculty. Kanunay mangumusta namo si father. Dayon ang mga faculty pud maam dili magdumili ug tabang namo nga mga security guard labina sa panahon sa pandemya mao nga mawala r pud ang among mga kabalaka”. [... we are so thankful to the school admin, maam because they are very supportive especially to father who always check on us. Then, some faculty members are very generous to us security guards especially during the pandemic, and it relieves our worries].SG9 said.

It's not only material and financial support that they received from the school admin and staff but also moral support. All ten (10) participants shared that the school admin kept checking their situations. They are so happy because the school treats them as part of the family.

"...We are so much thankful to them maam, pero ang among agency maam wala gyuy suporta nga gihatag bisan pa niadtong pahahon sa pandemya. Nagibog lang mi sa uban nga naay nadawat bisan ginagmay" [...We are so much thankful to the school admin and faculty for being so supportive, but our agency never bother to give even a little amount of support, ma'am]. SG5.

Participants emphasized the value of consistently working closely with teachers, administrators, and fellow security guards to implement safety protocols. They discussed the importance of open lines of communication, sharing information, and coordinating efforts to create a safe and secure school environment.

".. gani niadtong panahon nga nagkinahanglan ug quarantine pass maam, gihimuan gyud mi sa mga teachers aron naa mi magamit. Lipay gyud kaayo mi maam. [..In fact, at the time when quarantine pass is needed, the teachers made one for us security guards. We are so happy for it.] SG 5 claimed.

This theme highlights the essential role of teamwork and collaboration in navigating the challenges presented by the pandemic.

Engaging in peer support networks is a good coping strategy to mitigate emotional and psychological crises. Being connected with fellow security guards or professionals in similar roles to share experiences, exchange advice, and provide mutual support is a helpful way to maintain a work-life balance that may enable them to actively perform their roles and responsibilities free from worries and stress.

Understanding Vital Role. Participants spoke passionately about their role in ensuring the safety and well-being of the school community. They expressed a deep pride in their work and the fulfillment they derived from making a positive impact during challenging times. This theme highlights the dedication and resilience of security guards in fulfilling their responsibilities and underscores the importance of recognizing and appreciating their contributions. This theme underscores the shifting role of school security guards from solely focusing on physical security to being responsible for health and safety. The pandemic highlighted their vital role in maintaining a safe environment and supporting the well-being of students and staff.

Participants reported that health and safety are their main priorities. They have to be extra careful not only for their safety but also for the safety of everyone. Considering how alarming the COVID-19 virus is, it is not a joke once you are infected. Not only is your life at stake, but everyone's life. When one person is infected in the area, every resident is already facing the threat. The real enemy cannot be seen; we need to be careful not to be infected. One way to be safe is to follow standard health and safety protocols strictly. In schools and other establishments, the security guards are the core persons responsible for the implementation. According to one of the security guards, they are responsible for the safety of the people entering the campus. One way of showing concern to people is to strictly implement the protocols and ensure that everyone must follow them. Considering that they are the front liners, they also ensure they are healthy. SG 7 said:

".....doble ingat gyud mi maam. Observe gyud kanunay sa health and safety protocols kay syempre kami mn gyud ang moresib

sa mga bisita mao nga istrikto gyud mi maam sa mga customer nga mosulod diri sa eskwelahan maam, Kinahnaglan gyud nga ekstra kerpul gyud mi sa among kaugalingon maam dili lang para sa kaugalingon kon dili para pud sa safety sa among pamilya ug sa tanan.” [.....we need to be extra careful. We need to always observe also the health and safety protocols since we are the one who always received guestsnot only for our own safety but also for the safety of our family and everyone in the campus.] SG7

SG 4 added also:

“.....moagi man gyud namo ang tanan nga mosulod mao nga kinahanglan gyud nga istrikto namong ipatuman ang mga protocols sa tanan nga mosulod sa campus aron sa paglikay sa virus”. [...we are the first person to receive all the guests in the campus that’s why we really have to strictly implement the health and safety protocols to everyone who enter in the campus to avoid the virus] SG4.

Despite this positive intention, others did not understand, often leading to complaints, and worse, arguments often arise. People did not consider the reason behind the strict implementation of the protocols even though we already knew how life-threatening the COVID-19 virus was.

Unveiling Valuable Insights from the Experiences. This theme focuses on the valuable insights gained from the experiences of school security guards during the pandemic. This theme highlights the core values that can be extracted from the experiences of school security guards in the new normal. It encompasses values such as adaptability, resilience, commitment to safety, empathy, vigilance, teamwork and collaboration, professionalism, effective communication, problem-solving, and community engagement. The theme reflects the underlying principles and beliefs that guided the actions and behaviors of school security guards as they navigated the challenges and responsibilities in the face of the new normal.

School security guards demonstrated the value of being flexible and adaptable to changing circumstances and demands. They could easily adapt to the changing needs in their work, like the implementation of the health and safety protocols, which is an additional responsibility to them.

Aside from being adaptable, they also exhibited resilience in the face of adversity and uncertainty, finding ways to overcome challenges and maintain a safe environment. They are strong enough to stand at the height of the virus surge. They are not afraid to risk their own safety; rather, they continue to perform their duties and responsibilities as front liners.

Security guards also displayed a strong commitment to the safety and well-being of the school community, prioritizing the implementation of safety protocols and ensuring compliance. One participant shared:

“... our primary responsibility is to protect lives and property maam, hanggat makaya namo maam, ug mao gyud na amo tamdan kay mao mn amo gipanumpa’an”. [... our primary responsibility is to protect lives and property, and we must adhere to it because it is what we swore]. SG5.

Most participants said their experience in the pandemic has widened their knowledge of carrying out new roles and responsibilities.

“... mas gipalawom ang among kasinatian sa pagpamalaud. Mas nagkalantip usab ang among panglantaw tungod niining pang-hitabo. [... it deepen our understanding especially in implementing rules and policies. It also widen our perspective due this incident.] supported by SG4.

They also showed empathy and exemplified the value of being vigilant and proactive in monitoring and addressing potential risks and safety breaches towards students, staff, and their fellow security guards, understanding the emotional impact of the crisis and offering support and reassurance. They are vigilant about the students' behavior and watchful whenever anyone manifests symptoms of COVID-19.

They emphasized the importance of teamwork and collaboration with school administrators, teachers, and staff to ensure a cohesive approach to safety measures and crisis management as they continuously collaborate with the school staff and stakeholders. They never fail to demonstrate the value of clear and effective communication, conveying safety protocols to others and listening and addressing concerns and questions.

“.. bisan pa lisod ang among naagian atol sa pandemya pero mas nagkahugot ang among relasyon sa kauban. Bisan pa adunay dili pagsinabtanay pero dihadiha maresolba ra dayun. [... in spite of this difficult experiences during the pandemic but it strengthen our relationship with our workmates. Though there were slight misunderstanding but it is soon resolved.] SG 10 said.

As they carry out their duties and responsibilities, security guards-maintained professionalism in their roles, effectively balancing their responsibilities and adapting their practices to meet the new demands of the pandemic. They also exhibited problem-solving skills, finding innovative solutions to challenges that arose in implementing safety measures and adapting to the new normal, fostering a sense of unity and shared responsibility in navigating the new normal, and promoting a supportive and secure environment.

Most notably, essential themes from this study have distinguished the underlying values that have been extracted from the experiences of the school security guards. It has been known that the main duties and responsibilities of security guards are to protect lives and maintain order within the vicinity of their assigned (philgoldsecurityservices.com). This study indicates that security guards have faced varied challenges during the pandemic. And in times of crisis, it is the school that provides support. The security agency never bothers to extend any form of support during the pandemic except for the salary each security guard is entitled to.

The themes that arose were categorized into security guard experiences, challenges, and coping strategies. Three themes emerged in the experiences of the school security guards, namely: a) *Adapting to new Responsibilities*, b) *Monitoring and Securing Safety at all costs*, and c) *Feeling Proud Front Liners Amidst Risk*.

Meanwhile, there were five (5) themes also under the challenges of the school security guards during the pandemic, namely: a) *Defiance to the protocol*, b) *Disrespectful clients*, c) *Miscommunication with peers and workmates*, d) *Deficient time for family*, and e) *Difficulty in Adapting to new demands*.

School security guards have identified four (4) themes as their coping strategies to meet the evolving demands and mitigate emotional and psychological crises brought on by the pandemic. These themes are the following: a) Understanding vital role, b) *Sticking to policy to ensure safety*, c) Fostering a sense of collaboration, and d) *Seeking support and maintaining open communication*.

To sum up, the experiences of the school security guard during the pandemic provide ideas to all school personnel that security guards play a vital role in maintaining peace and order on the school premises. Despite the tough tasks assigned to them, they still manage to perform all their duties and responsibilities, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. The themes that emerged from this study are the essential themes that enable us to extract values from the experiences of these security guards. It encompasses values such as adaptability, resilience, commitment to safety, empathy, vigilance, teamwork and collaboration, professionalism, effective communication, problem-solving, and community engagement.

The COVID-19 pandemic is one of the big challenges that brought change to the entire operation worldwide, and this concretely measures the level of resilience of the school security guards behind the adversity of the pandemic. Catherine Moore's resilience theory has proven the idea that whatever circumstances bring change, we can easily cope with it (Moore,2019). In this study, security guards have demonstrated their coping in overcoming the challenges and stressors brought by the COVID-19 pandemic. The resiliency fostered by most security guards to withstand adversities has clearly illustrated the idea of the Adversity Quotient Theory of Paul Stoltz (Stoltz, 1997).

Implications

School security significantly impacts learning performance, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. School security measures can support learning continuity during the pandemic. Once school safety and security are secured, these help increase the feeling of safety and comfort of both learners and staff. However, poorly implemented security measures can lead to feelings of discomfort and anxiety among the learners and staff, and this would interfere with learning.

The findings of this study have important implications for supporting and protecting school operations during the pandemic and in the future. School authorities, policymakers, and other stakeholders must understand the unique challenges that school security guards faced during the pandemic and take steps to support and protect them. This may include providing personal protective equipment, additional training, and financial assistance to help mitigate security guards' financial difficulties. Furthermore, it is important to consider the role of school security guards in ensuring the safety of the school community, providing them with the necessary resources and support to perform their duties effectively, and ensuring effective and successful school operations.

Practical implications: The findings of this study provide insights into the challenges and experiences of school security guards during the pandemic. School administrators and policymakers can use this information to improve policies and practices related to school safety and security during times of crisis.

Humanistic implications: The study highlights the experiences of a group of school employees who are often overlooked or undervalued. By bringing attention to their experiences, the study can help to humanize the role of school security guards and promote a more empathetic and supportive school culture.

Research implications: The study adds to the literature on school safety and security during the pandemic, particularly from the perspective of school security guards. The study's

methodology and findings may also inform future research on this topic, particularly related to qualitative research methods and semi-structured interviews.

Societal implications: The study's findings contribute to broader conversations about the impact of the pandemic on essential workers and those who work in public-facing roles. By exploring the experiences of school security guards, the study can shed light on the challenges faced by other essential workers and promote a more nuanced understanding of the pandemic's social and economic impacts.

Overall, this study has significant implications for improving school safety and security during times of crisis, promoting a more humanistic approach to school security, advancing qualitative research methods in this area, and contributing to broader conversations about the impact of the pandemic on essential workers.

Summary of Findings

This study aimed to gather data on the experiences of the school security guards serving in catholic schools during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings of this study revealed several key insights into the experiences of school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic. The researcher came up with the following findings:

Question 1: What were the experiences of a school security guard during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Participants expressed a sense of heightened responsibility and the need to adapt quickly to the changing circumstances. Security guards demonstrated their ability to quickly adapt and respond to the evolving demands of their roles, focusing on enforcing COVID-19 safety measures such as mask usage, social distancing, and temperature checks. They also demonstrated their passion for closely monitoring and securing the safety of all individuals within the premises. They reported increased stress and anxiety due to the uncertainty surrounding the virus and the potential risks they faced while working in the school environment. Additionally, security guards described feelings of pride in contributing to the safety of the school community during such a challenging time being a front liner.

Research Question 2: How did they adapt to the evolving demands of their role during the pandemic?

Security guards exhibited a strong sense of purpose and commitment to their roles in ensuring the safety and well-being of the school community. They took pride in their work and found fulfillment in making a positive impact during challenging times. Participants reported adjusting their routines and protocols to prioritize COVID-19 safety measures, such as implementing and enforcing mask usage, monitoring social distancing, and conducting temperature checks. They described attending training sessions, leveraging technology, and collaborating with other school staff to stay updated on changing guidelines and protocols. This adaptability allowed them to effectively balance their traditional duties as security guards with the new demands of the COVID-19 pandemic. Sticking to policy and adhering to the standard safety protocols is enable to adapt successfully to the new demands brought by the pandemic.

Research Question 3: What challenges did they face in ensuring the implementation of safety protocols?

Security guards faced challenges enforcing safety protocols, particularly about mask usage and social distancing. Resistance from some students, staff, parents and limited resources hindered their ability to carry out their responsibilities effectively. Participants mentioned difficulties in enforcing mask usage and social distancing among students, particularly

with younger children who found it challenging to understand and follow these guidelines consistently. They also encountered resistance or pushback from some students, staff, and parents, who may not fully understand or agree with the necessity of the safety protocols, which enable them to heighten their stress and add to their challenges. Thus, difficulty in adapting to the new demands became a burden to them at first. Additionally, participants expressed concerns about their safety, such as vulnerability to the virus, and the lack of adequate resources, such as personal protective equipment (PPE) or sanitization supplies, to carry out their responsibilities effectively. Moreover, miscommunication with peers and workmates due to the protocols was marked as one of their challenges. At the same time, deficient time for the family due to the restrictions and workloads added another challenge to them.

Research Question 4: What coping strategies did they employ to address the emotional and psychological impact of the crisis?

Security guards experienced heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and fear during the pandemic. They employed coping strategies such as seeking support from colleagues, maintaining communication with loved ones, and fostering a sense of camaraderie within their team to address the emotional and psychological impact of the crisis. They also mentioned finding solace in regular communication with family and loved ones outside of work to alleviate stress and anxiety. School security guards have sought support from colleagues, friends, or family members to share their concerns, fears, and experiences related to the crisis. This highlights the importance of social support in managing emotional and psychological challenges. Engaging in self-care activities, such as exercise, hobbies, or mindfulness practices, is also advisable to maintain their well-being during challenging times.

Research Question 5: What values can be extracted from the experiences of school security in the new normal?

Participants emphasized the importance of adaptability, resilience, and a strong sense of responsibility toward the safety and well-being of the school community. They recognized the value of effective communication, collaboration, and teamwork in navigating the challenges of the pandemic. Additionally, the experiences highlighted the significance of empathy, patience, and understanding when interacting with students, staff, and parents with different perspectives or concerns. The data analysis also revealed the value of continuous learning, staying updated on guidelines and protocols, and seeking professional development opportunities.

Conclusions

The study provides valuable insights into the experiences of school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic. It has shed light on the unique experiences of school security guards as frontline workers during the COVID-19 pandemic. While much attention has been given to healthcare professionals and other essential workers, the role of security guards has been overlooked. This study showed the distinctive challenges and responsibilities faced by the school security guards in maintaining the safety and security of the school administrators, school employees, students, and stakeholders during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The findings have implications for policy development, support systems, collaboration, and recognition within the school community. To enhance school security during a crisis, it is crucial to provide security guards with the necessary resources, training, and support to adapt to new roles and responsibilities. Collaborative efforts, effective communication, and stakeholder engagement are key to ensuring the consistent implementation of safety protocols. Recognizing and appreciating the contributions of security guards fosters a positive work environment and reinforces their sense of purpose and commitment. By addressing the identified findings and

implementing the recommended implications, educational institutions can create a safer and more resilient environment for the entire school community during and beyond the pandemic.

The analysis of qualitative data collected from interviews with school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic provided valuable insights into their experiences, adaptations, challenges, coping strategies, and the values they derived from their roles. The findings emphasize the need for ongoing support, resources, and training for school security guards to address the evolving demands and ensure the implementation of safety protocols. Recognizing and appreciating the experiences of security guards can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of their crucial role in maintaining a safe and secure school environment in the new normal.

Recommendations

Driven by the findings in this study, the researcher came up with the following recommendations:

Future researchers may conduct similar research on the lived experiences of the security guards but focus more on a deeper life understanding of the different aspects of security, not only covering experiences in a particular phenomenon. Different aspects of a security guard's life might be discovered and understood.

The different security agencies may develop and implement comprehensive training programs tailored to school security guards' evolving roles and responsibilities during a pandemic. Programs that focus on crisis management, conflict resolution, effective communication, and enforcing safety protocols. Regularly update and evaluate the training to address emerging challenges and ensure guards are well-prepared to navigate future crises.

Moreover, security agencies may fund and support studies on their agency and security personnel to better understand their employees. They may also be prompt and responsible in providing social services to their employees and delivering efficient service to them.

Government officials may include in their program of activities a unique program that assists all security guards, especially during calamities. Moreover, they may take action against every security company that is not prompt in delivering social services to their employees.

School administrators may provide soft skills activities to maintain mental well-being. In coordination with the security agency, the school may establish support systems for security guards that might address their emotional and psychological well-being. This includes providing access to counseling services, stress management resources, and regular check-ins to assess their needs and provide necessary support.

School employees may also support the security guards in enforcing safety and security protocols of the school even after the pandemic. Every school personnel must check the students' behavior and consistently impose discipline.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Trustworthiness and Ethical Considerations

Trustworthiness refers to the confidence level in the data analysis and methods used, which guarantees the quality of the study (Wa-Mbaleka & Rosario, 2022; Polit & Beck, 2014). Creswell (2007) and Creswell and Clark (2011) define trustworthiness as the researcher's effort to measure the study's quality and acceptability of its findings. A specific and detailed approach was utilized to maximize trustworthiness in this study. Using Creswell's (2013) validation

strategies, this study used member checking, dependability or rich, thick descriptions, peer review, and frequent debriefing sessions.

Ethical considerations are paramount in conducting research, especially when studying human participants. In the case of this study on the experiences of school security guards during the COVID-19 pandemic, the following ethical considerations were observed:

Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation

Before conducting the interview, informed consent was given to the participants, clearly stating the aim or purpose of conducting the personal interview and reassuring them of confidentiality and anonymity. Further, they were informed that their participation in the study was voluntary.

Participants signed the voluntary and informed consent to participate in the study. They were fully aware of the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, the potential risks and benefits, and their rights as participants. Informed consent was documented through a consent form, and participants were informed that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any negative consequences.

Confidentiality and Anonymity

Participants' confidentiality and anonymity were protected throughout the research process. All collected data, including interview transcripts and audio recordings, are securely stored and accessible only to the research team. Participants' identities were protected by using pseudonyms or coding s when reporting the findings. SG represents the security guard, SF represents the school faculty, HSS represents the high school students, and CS for the college students.

Data Privacy

This research has considered the importance of data privacy and has considered the principles and regulations in the Data Privacy Act to ensure the protection of personal data. Before accessing the research environment, the researcher obtained necessary permissions and approvals from relevant authorities, such as school administrations. All sensitive or personal information shared by participants is handled with utmost care and kept confidential.

Minimization of Harm

Researchers should take precautions to minimize potential harm or distress to participants. This includes conducting interviews in a supportive and empathetic manner, allowing participants to skip or decline answering sensitive questions, and offering debriefing or follow-up support if needed.

Ethical Approval

Securing approval is a necessary process to be considered before conducting a study (Rosario & Wa-Mbaleka, 2022). Before conducting this study, the proposal has been approved. Before gathering the necessary data from the participants, the researcher sought first approval from the President of the Diocesan Schools. Before conducting an interview, another approval was sought by the researcher to the respective Vice President for Administration in each campus (Appendix)

Dependability

Rich and thick descriptions of the experience were used to increase the transferability of the study (Lincoln & Guba, 1986) and allow the reader to understand the phenomenon more fully

and clearly (Moustakas, 1994). The researcher described the methodology and the participant's experiences (Rosario & Wa-Mbaleka, 2022; Shenton, 2004). According to Creswell (2013), detailed descriptions allowed us to transfer the meanings and essences of a certain study to other locations to determine the applicability of the findings to other contexts reflecting the lived experiences of security guards in particular situations. Noting the shared characteristics among the descriptions made the findings more transferable (Creswell, 2013; Lincoln & Guba, 1986). In addition, describing the details required multiple participant quotes and an active participant voice (Creswell, 2013). Aside from this, the findings in this study have been checked and compared to the findings of other related published studies. Varied relevant theories were examined and compared for validity and accuracy.

Frequent Debriefing Sessions. In this study, debriefing sessions between the researcher and the research adviser were conducted to present updates on the study and its data analysis. Shenton (2004, in *the book of Rosario & Wa-Mbaleka, 2022*) mentioned that discussions during debriefing sessions offer opportunities to widen the researcher's vision. Further, this also provides a sounding board to test the researcher's developing ideas and perception to recognize her biases and preferences (Shenton, 2004).

Peer Review

Lastly, a peer review provided an additional check of the research by examination of the research methods, data collection, analysis, and meanings (Creswell, 2013). The researcher sought the expert's assistance to validate this study's findings. In addition, a peer review allowed the researcher to gain insight from a trusted peer from a sympathetic source. The peer was a full pledge doctoral degree holder. She is the Vice President for Academic Affairs in our institution. The peer edited the manuscript for style, form, and content. Most of the changes she suggested were writing technicality, grammar, syntax structure, and the study structure itself. She commented that the findings were thoroughly backed with participants' quotes, and the recommendations were rooted in the emerging themes and implications. Another peer was proficient in qualitative research. Most of his corrections fall under content relevance and organization, operational terms, and theoretical underpinnings. He commented that recommendations have addressed all the themes that have been identified.

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